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CREATING A FLEXIBLE PEDAGOGICAL QUALIFICATION PROGRAM AT A GERMAN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

A high quality engineering education builds, amongst other things on pedagogically competent teachers. Thus, to strategically qualify all involved teachers at a university is desirable; but in Germany it is still voluntary. Recently, a German University of Technology established an obligatory pedagogical qualification program for all research assistants employed under university's budget. This short paper highlights the program design, the first evaluation and present participants' reaction. A 60 hour, maximum two year lasting program that is flexible, individualized, needs-based and hands-on with foci on "Higher Education & Engineering Pedagogy" and "Research-Based Learning" was designed. Intending to empower participants' pedagogical competencies, the program consists of an initial consultation, workshops, complementary elements and a final event. First of all, it is questioned how participants react to the program. Therefore, registrations were investigated and quantitative surveys carried out before and after three months of running the program. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. First, results indicate positive participants' reaction to the program while individual pathways play an important role, such as key program characteristics. Secondly, results indicate that pedagogical competence acquisition takes place early in the program and is important for participant reaction but is limited for now. Thirdly, besides the program

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design, participants attitudes and supervisors support are relevant factors for participant reaction and proper learning. It is planned to detect the participants' reaction, learning and future teaching prospective after completing the program using a mixed-method approach, to develop the program further and to find university wide solutions besides the program itself.

1 INTRODUCTION

High-impact educational practices need to meet enabling conditions and must overcome multiple obstacles (e.g. [1], [2], [3]). Among others, developing academics' pedagogical competence is key in implementing modern engineering education as shown exemplary at a German University of Technology (see [4]). In Germany however, pedagogical training still relies mostly on single voluntary workshops. Only exceptionally, training programs are obligatory for special target groups. These programs face limited participants' acceptance (see [5]). Importantly, participants' acceptance of a program has a decisive influence on participants' learning success within it; and this in turn on their prospective intentions in teaching practice (see [6]). To address this, a German University of Technology recently introduced a more flexible, obligatory pedagogical qualification program called I³ProTeachING [7]. This short paper gives brief insights into the pilot phase of this program by firstly emphasizing the program design and evaluation and secondly, highlighting how participants react to this flexible program at the very beginning of the program.

2 METHODOLOGY

To ensure and enhance high quality education, the Executive Committee of a German University of Technology initiated a qualification program on interdisciplinary and innovative teaching in engineering for all research assistants employed under the university's budget. It commissioned its center for teaching and learning to implement a training in cooperation with the university's graduate academy. Based on earlier experiences (see [4], [5]), it was required to design a flexible, 60 hour program within max. two years and variable enrolment date.

2.1 Designing a pedagogical program

It is aimed that participants are able to discuss pedagogical principles, apply methods and media in teaching, develop their teaching personality, present a teaching related product and network on the subject of teaching across institutes after completing the program. Therefore, participants choose one competence line: (1) "Higher Pedagogy & Engineering Education" (HP/ EE) according to [8] or (2) "Research-Based Learning" (RBL) according to [9] and [10]. Participants inform themselves at an information event, they arrange an initial individual conversation, select core and accompanying workshops from a quite broad catalogue, conduct three complementary elements, namely reflection (each person alone), peer visit (2 persons) and teaching project (up to 3 persons), and join a final event. In the final event, participants present and discuss their teaching project product (e.g. a poster) with the university's community and are rewarded with the certificates which are

acknowledged in the graduate academy's phd supplement. Within the program, participants make use of *Mahara* as e-portfolio and collaboration platform. In total, they experience a variety of teaching and learning methods and media within the program. The participants' learning outcomes are assessed during the program by peers and educational developers and after completing the program by the participants themselves in an online survey. Educational developers mentor the participants in almost all program components. Participants compile their program based on their interests and needs. In summary, it was aimed to offer an individualized and hands-on program that allows flexibility in content and time and orientate on participants' desires and university's goals.

2.2 Evaluating the pedagogical program

To start evaluating the program in the first implementation phase, it was focussed on how participants react to the program. The evaluation was designed according to the first level of evaluating training programs [6]. One assumption was made here: The program design has to be flexible to create a positive participant reaction. Registrations were investigated, one self-designed online questionnaire was conducted prior to the program (n=8 of 37) and a second after three months (n=15 of 31, with only 4 RBL participants). Descriptive statistical analyses were conducted. At this time, interviews have not yet been conducted.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Participants' reaction to the program – program design aspects

As mentioned in the questionnaire before the program started (n=8), respondents find the content and time related flexibility very important (see Fig. 1). Remarkably prior to the start, program characteristics like orientation towards the real needs of teachers and hands-on characteristics (e.g. concrete tips and pedagogical methods in teaching practice) or the scientific basis of the program (e.g. pedagogical principles and theoretical background) were seen as very important or important, too. After three months, most persons valued the individual program compilation as important for themselves (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 1 Agreement on importance of program characteristics, therein, 1...totally agree and 4...totally disagree, arithmetic mean and standard deviation are shown, questionnaire prior to the program start (n=8)

Fig. 2 Number of responses on importance of flexibility, questionnaire three months after program start (n=14)

This is reflected by participants' registrations and their perception of some program characteristic after three months: Firstly, most persons (31 of 37) registered to start the program directly. Both competence lines experienced similar registration numbers (HP/ EE: 13 persons; RBL: 17; one person was undecided). Besides the initial workshop (joined by 14 participants in each competence line), most RBL participants (n=14) directly selected one core workshop with a central topic namely developing RBL, while HP/ EE participants selected four core workshops on various pedagogical topics (supervising & assessing written work, designing assessment, explaining & asking understandable; n varied between 1 and 4 persons). Almost all participants conducted initial conversations and many participated in workshops. Secondly, in the questionnaire after three months (n=15), respondents perceived their selected "competence line" to be interesting or very interesting (12 of 13 persons) and to be relevant or very relevant for their teaching (11 of 12 persons). Free text responses indicate that participants selected workshops because they met their interests in improving courses, they addressed daily teaching challenges or enabled them to exchange experiences on a specific topic. Interestingly, after three months, respondents perceive the program as relevant or very relevant for their recent research (7 of 14 persons) and prospective career (9 of 14 persons). However, after three months four respondents deemed the program as slightly hindering due to the time it involved adding to the already busy daily workload. To shed light on participant reaction, it is focussed in the next chapter on participants' learning at the beginning of the program, their attitude prior to the program and supervisors' support.

3.2 Participants' reaction to the program – participants' learning in the beginning

Prior to the start of the program, respondents (n=8) perceive all intended program learning outcomes on higher education pedagogy as important or very important. Interestingly, after three months, participants stated similar learning goals like enhancing teaching quality or exchanging with others. Furthermore, HE/ EE respondents assess to have good fundamental pedagogical competencies, despite handling teaching challenges (n=9). On the contrary, RBL respondents presume to have moderate RBL competencies (n=4), despite higher presumed competencies in brainstorming ideas for implementing research-based learning. Respondents experienced the initial conversation, workshops and *Mahara* as helpful to achieve their goals at the beginning of their program.

3.3 Participants' reaction to the program – aspects besides the program design

Firstly, responses (n = 8) before the start of the program point to a positive participants' teaching attitude. Exemplary, respondents perceived developing teaching quality at this university as fundamentally important, engaging in teaching as joyful and a pedagogical qualification and their personal participation as rather important or rather appropriate. Secondly, evaluation results indicate that participants perceive supervisors' support as important and that they feel supported

by their supervisors. Concretely, prior to the program start (n=8), respondents mentioned proactive support by their supervisors as important. After three months, 12 of 13 respondents stated they felt their supervisors' tolerance, support or explicit encouragement regarding their program participation.

4 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

A flexible, obligatory pedagogical qualification program for research assistants at a German University of Technology was designed and evaluated. It should be strongly highlighted that the meaning of the results presented here needs cautious interpretation and is not conclusive due to relative low response numbers in questionnaires and since we did not yet conduct interviews. However, based on the results presented here, predominantly positive respondents' program reaction before starting and at the beginning of conducting it was detected. It is argued here that an obligatory pedagogical program should offer individual pathways among other key program characteristics in order to create positive participants' reaction. Moreover, it is claimed that quick learning is important for a positive participants' reaction. However, complex pedagogical competence achievement is envisaged to develop over time in several program components. Additionally, it is desired that a program approach includes interaction with supervisors, breathing space in the busy daily workschedule and the use of challenges in teaching practice as a starting point for academics' qualifications and implementation of high-impact educational practice for advancing students' engineering competencies. Importantly, although some findings might indicate to be in-line with results of earlier studies (see [4], [5]), several aspects remain open in this small concept study. Hence, further attempts will be made (1) to further evaluate the program on the levels of reaction, learning and behavior after participants' program completion using both quantitative (questionnaires) as well as qualitative methods (interviews), (2) to develop the program correspondingly further and strengthen thereby the connection to a strong competence development framework for research assistants and (3) to act strategically on dimensions that frame the pedagogical program such as teaching culture and resources.

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